

Intelligent Enough? Evaluating Collective Action in HOT Tasking Manager Mapping Projects

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Humanitarian mapping projects coordinated through the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team Tasking Manager (HOT-TM) represent a paradigmatic case of large-scale digital collaboration. Yet, while their practical utility in disaster response and preparedness is increasingly evident, the underlying collective dynamics that allow these efforts to function effectively remain under-explored. This talk builds on our recent article published in ACM Transactions on Computer-Human Interaction (TOCHI) [1] that presents a comprehensive analysis of HOT-TM projects through the lens of collective intelligence.

Collective Intelligence is defined as “groups of individuals acting collectively in ways that seem intelligent [2].” Following this definition, we structured our analysis around three guiding research questions: (RQ1) What characterizes the group of individuals collaborating in HOT-TM mapping projects?, (RQ2) How is collective action organized within these projects?, and (RQ3) What evidence of intelligent action can be identified in this setting?

To answer these questions, we constructed and analyzed a dataset encompassing 746 HOT-TM projects executed between December 2021 and November 2023. Additionally, we incorporated spatial information on the area of mapped buildings using data extracted from the OpenStreetMap database. The methodology consisted of three main components. First, an initial profiling of 38,893 contributors was conducted using descriptive statistics, focusing on experience levels (beginner, intermediate, advanced), geographic location, and profile completeness. This allowed the authors to assess contributors' mapping activity, regional participation patterns, and profile richness. Second, to characterize collective action, process mining techniques were applied to over 1.8 million state transitions captured in HOT-TM event logs¹. Each task was treated as a case, with its sequence of mapping and

¹ We have made available a code repository with Python and R notebooks that document in detail the procedures followed for data collection, preprocessing, and analysis in this study. The link is <https://github.com/IAAA-Lab/Collective-Intelligence-in-Humanitarian-Voluntary-Geographic-Information-ODECO-HOT-TM>.

validation states represented as an activity trace. Using the *bupaR* package in R, we generated directly-follows graphs and trace frequency maps to reconstruct typical workflows. Performance overlays allowed us to examine state durations, throughput times, and bottlenecks. We also analyzed handover of work patterns, identifying when and how tasks moved between contributors, and measured the degree of sequential collaboration during mapping and validation phases. The analysis distinguished between individual and collaborative contributions and explored how these patterns varied by contributor expertise and project characteristics. Third, a logistic regression model was employed to investigate factors associated with task validation outcomes—used as indicators of collective intelligent action. The model included variables related to contributor attributes (e.g., experience level, location, number of contributors per task), task characteristics (e.g., building area mapped, validation time), and project-level controls (e.g., difficulty and priority).

Results show that the vast majority of contributors are beginners, who typically participate in a single project. However, a small group of highly experienced mappers—classified by HOT-TM as "advanced"—contribute to dozens of projects and assume more complex tasks. Notably, only 29% of contributors declare their country, but among those who do, the majority are based outside the regions affected by the mapping projects. This reinforces existing concerns about the limited presence of local knowledge in humanitarian Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI) initiatives [3].

Most mapping tasks are directly mapped and then validated without being split or invalidated, with a small percentage of tasks deviating from the main path (see Figure 1). However, tasks that involve higher complexity or suffer errors require more contributors and longer processing times. Roles within the mapping system are clearly stratified: while beginners dominate mapping in simpler projects, advanced mappers take the lead in complex cases and are responsible for nearly all validations. Despite the potential for collaboration in the mapping phase—through the sequential editing of tasks—true interdependence among contributors is limited. Most tasks are executed by a single mapper, and where collaboration occurs, it is often sequential and uncoordinated. This suggests that HOT-TM's microtasking design promotes a form of "collection" rather than "collaboration" [4].

Figure 1. Frequency and duration map of task states and transitions (85% of most frequent traces).

We find that advanced contributors are significantly more likely to produce validated outputs, especially when working alone. However, involving multiple contributors in a task—especially when they are less experienced—decreases the probability of successful validation. Furthermore, tasks with larger building areas or those requiring extensive validation times are less likely to be validated, suggesting that complexity and ambiguity remain major challenges.

These findings highlight a paradox at the heart of humanitarian mapping: although the system succeeds in rapidly mobilizing volunteers to produce useful geographic data, its collective intelligence is unevenly distributed and relies heavily on a small core of experienced contributors. The wisdom of the crowd is therefore not uniformly distributed; rather, it is the wisdom of a few that sustains the productivity and reliability of the system. Moreover, the absence of strong collaborative mechanisms and the limited engagement of local mappers constrain the potential for adaptive and context-aware mapping.

We conclude by reflecting on possible design improvements for platforms like HOT-TM. These include: (1) enhancing onboarding and mentorship to accelerate the transition from beginner to advanced contributor; (2) incentivizing meaningful collaboration beyond sequential task handovers; and (3) integrating local knowledge more effectively by prioritizing and rewarding contributions from mappers with relevant geographic proximity or contextual expertise. These directions not only aim to improve the efficiency of mapping but also address the deeper goal of fostering sustainable, inclusive, and context-aware humanitarian VGI ecosystems.

This work contributes to the growing body of research at the intersection of Human-Computer Interaction, Collective Intelligence, and Geographic Information Science, and provides empirical grounding for future interventions in humanitarian mapping systems.

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Conflicts of Interest: Héctor Ochoa-Ortiz is a member of the OpenStreetMap Foundation board of directors, as well, he is the president of Asociación OpenStreetMap España. He does not represent these organizations in this document.

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